

MAGISTRLAR CERTIFICATE

OF ACHIEVEMENT

... PROUDLY ...
PRESENTED TO

Safarov Mirjalol

AQLI ZAIF BOLALARNI TARBIYALASH VA TA'LIM BERISH, ULARNING MUSTAQIL

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